

Preparation of a Startup Business Plan through Online Training for Millennial Entrepreneurs in Indonesia

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Abstract: *More and more young people who belong to the millennial generation and generation Z want to start a startup business. The development of startup businesses in the internet environment is also growing. Therefore, young people who are members of SEPex Young Yogyakarta and Kevikepan DIY Province in Indonesia are also interested in building with the motivation to create massive new jobs for young people. The main problem is that those who are involved in the development or development of the business do not have good, neat, logical, efficient and effective planning. Therefore, through this community service program, partners need motivation, debriefing or training, practice making startup business plans, evaluation, and correction. Through this program, the participants gain insight, knowledge and skills in preparing a startup business plan that is ready to be implemented.*

Keywords: *startup business, business plan, online training,*

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, young people who become the productive workforce consist of the millennial generation (Y generation) who were born between 1980-1996 and generation Z who were born starting in 1997. At present, the millennial generation is the largest productive workforce. While followed by the first generation Z generation who began to enter the productive working age (Stillman&Stillman, 2017). Based on observations, it is suspected that from the millennial generation there have been significant changes. The millennial workforce seems to be starting to avoid "office jobs" or becoming company employees. They do not want to work under bonded hours. On the other hand, they want to be independent by maximizing the technology in their hands to build a business. The condition was formed not solely by their wish. However, this condition was created because it was triggered by a movement to give birth to young entrepreneurs which was proclaimed by the government (Kasali, 2010) in a structured, systematic and massive manner in Indonesia. Like a tit for tat, the millennial generation welcomes a new era in the world of work with joy and enthusiasm. They also become agents of changing vision and work practices today (Tapscott, 2009). Not felt as the formation of society 4.0 (Kartajaya, 2017) there has been a disruption (Kasali, 2017) from the desire to work in a company to a desire to work independently. Especially in the industrial era 4.0, information technology devices have been able to provide control and response to various business processes, so that business practices have begun to experience major changes (Savitri, 2019).

Therefore, it is very appropriate if the millennial generation continues to be encouraged to become young entrepreneurs (Hendro, 2011a). Where, they can start establishing information technology-based startups or what is often referred to as a business startup (Ramdhan, 2016). In general, in the development of a startup business, there are many problems, challenges and obstacles faced by young people, including young people who are members of the Yogyakarta Young Executive Personal Evangelization School (SEPexMuda) and young people who are under the guidance of the Kevikepan Catholic Charismatic Renewal Service Agency. (Kev BPPKK) DIY. Young people who will be involved in a startup business are not only required to be able to develop and solidify online marketing strategies alone (Kunto, 2014) in the face of very competitive competition today (Kotler, Kartajaya, & Huan, 2017). However, they also have to really understand all the processes starting from the preparation of business startup planning (Viki, Toma, & Gons, 2019), designing product values (Osterwalder, Pigneur, Bernarda, & Smith, 2019), fostering company value (Djaja, 2017), building a business model (Osterwalder&Pigneur, 2012) that is efficient and competitive (ER, 2018), as well as aspects of capital (Hendro, 2011b).

II. PROBLEM

Of the problems, challenges and obstacles faced by young people in developing the startup business, partners, namely SEPexMuda Yogyakarta and BP PKK Kevikepan DIY Indonesia have identified the essential problems of young people under their guidance which are a priority to be overcome, namely the preparation of startups. business plan.

This issue has become a major priority, because a number of young people who are members of the two partners who started building startup businesses for the sake of creating new jobs have not made significant progress, even tend to stagnate. From the evaluation, it was concluded that the main problem arose from the absence of a structured, systematic, objective and mature planning. Therefore, partners need an understanding, as well as the right practice of preparing a startup business plan, so that the startup business development can be restarted immediately, so that massive new job opportunities are created that are in line with the expectations of the Millennial generation and Z generation.

III. PROBLEM SOLUTION

To answer the needs of partners, this community service activity will apply several implementation methods, so that the goals of the partners can be achieved. As for some of these methods, namely:

a. Registration of participants

After a certain period from July 2020 to November 2020, there were 22 participants and 1 assistant who participated in the training for the preparation of a startup business plan. And the day before the activity started (November 6th 2020) data collection on participants was circulated by filling in the initial data consisting of: full name; a business to be built or developed; is the business already operating? If it is already operating, what are the obstacles?; if still in the planning stage, describe the plan that has been prepared.

Below are examples of participant profiles:

No	Name	Business Sector	Note
1	Michael Santosa	Cullinary	Already operating within a circle of close acquaintances. Online marketing is not yet used. Constraints on consumer expansion. Had a try to using Instagram and Facebook, but not yet impacted.
2	Andi Muliadi	Wholesale of sandals and shoes	Business has run conventionally. Want to pioneer into online patterns. Currently, still trying to organize finance and taxation, inventory is piling up.
3	Amelia	Fozen Food	Previously, she was running a fast food business, looking to expand into Frozen Food. The issue of how to expand the market, stable expedition, appropriate packaging, social media for online marketing.

b. Give motivation to participant

At the beginning of the training, participants were given motivation. This method is applied to motivate the participants in starting the preparation of a startup business plan, because it requires resilience, persistence and thoroughness to detect all related factors, explore supporting data, carry out careful calculations, and make wise decisions.

c. Training on the preparation of a startup business plan

Due to Covid-19 pandemic, training is conducted online, because offline training is not yet possible. The method used is in the form of a lecture to provide cognitive provisions in the form of information and knowledge about everything related to the startup business plan preparation process (material can be read in the attachment section). In addition, a question and answer session was opened to share perceptions between the participants and the trainer. After assessing that the participants understand the material, the participants are given an assignment.

d. Feedback

After the material briefing on the first day by Singgih Santoso (November 7th 2020), participants were given feedback in the form of a question: What can be understood from today's material? Does marketing knowledge

inspire improvements to your business planning? What changes will be made to the business planning that has been made?

e. Practice making a startup business plan

This method is applied to provide real experiences for participants in preparing a startup business plan. With hands-on practice, participants will have skills in compiling a startup business plan. Until this report was compiled, only 4 participants had provided their plans, while 18 other participants were still trying to compile them.

Below are examples of participant feedback after training:

No	Name	What can be understood from today's material?	Does marketing knowledge inspire repair?	What changes will be made to planning business?
1	Michael Santosa	Business concepts, marketing mix, value proposition	Yes	Brand image building, build own web-site
2	Andi Muliadi	Market demand, branding, positioning, value proposition	Yes	Market demand, make own brand, value proposition
3	Amelia	Value, target market, branding And packaging.	Yes	

DISCUSSION

The participants were quite interested in providing a startup (e-) business plan preparation and training. Especially in terms of the knowledge presented to them. In table 3.2, it appears that the participants gained a lot of insight, knowledge and skills presented in the briefing on the first day. Meanwhile, from table 3.3, information was obtained about the elements that participants felt were known to them. From this data, it appears that the elements known to the participants are still incomplete when compared to the material to be delivered which reviews 16 elements, consisting of:

- a. Business Description
- b. Product Analysis
- c. Supply & Production Capacity Analysis
- d. Developer & Manager HR Analysis
- e. Situation & market analysis (online)
- f. Analysis of startup site services
- g. Analysis of Availability of Facilities & Technology
- h. Marketing & Promotion Strategy Analysis (online)
- i. Sales Strategy Analysis
- j. Marketspace and Marketplace analysis
- k. Financial & capital analysis
- l. Legal feasibility analysis
- m. Design & Building analysis
- n. Communication & Interaction Analysis
- o. Distribution & Transportation Analysis
- p. Site Evaluation & Maintenance

Moreover, after being provided with the debriefing, what the participants initially felt was known, in fact their knowledge was still incomplete. This can be seen from the three startup business plans that have been collected. Where, the participant's assessment of the elements of business planning is still very simple and limited.

The lack of detail in the startup business plans prepared by the participants was because they had not conducted an in-depth study of these elements. They even got the elements that needed to be studied only

during the debriefing. So, they only just put together a startup business plan that has been temporarily thought out and discussed with their partners in building a business.

For Vina and Diana, they have tried to touch 15 of the 16 elements in preparing a business plan, but they are still not detailed in presenting their study. It is also because there are many elements that have not been thought of at first, so they have not conducted an in-depth and detailed study.

In general, participants still stuttered in compiling a startup business plan for their business. However, at least through this provision and training, the participants gain insight, knowledge and skills, especially regarding the elements that must be considered and studied in preparation for building a business, both conventional and electronic.

Currently, participants are still trying to compile a business plan according to the directions given, as they are trying to make these businesses a reality by 2021. This shows that they have benefited from the training.

In addition, partners feel that they have benefited, so they need similar activities in the following years, as revealed in the thank-you letter from the two partners in this community service activity and partner survey (see attachment).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusion Based on the community service activities that have been carried out, it can be concluded: a. The debriefing and training activities for the preparation of a startup business plan have opened up insights, increased knowledge and increased the skills of the participants, so that they can improve, complete and perfect their business development and development plans. b. The insights and knowledge provided have changed the mindset of the participants in preparing a business plan, so it takes time to conduct an in-depth and detailed study of the 16 elements of a startup business plan that have been studied together during the debriefing activities.

2. Suggestion Based on participants' impressions and expectations of community service activity partners as stated in partner surveys and thank-you letters, similar activities and follow-up activities, such as training on brand strengthening, sales techniques, and consumer patterns based on socio-economic status related to startup business need to be held at the coming years.

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